

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

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Data and variables

The graphs presented in this supplementary document include only research outputs with two or more citations. Two different diversity measures are used to represent the level of diversity in citing actors, i.e., the Gini-Simpson index and the Shannon index. Data from 2010 to 2019 (both inclusive) as publication years are presented. Diversity measures are calculated based on grouping all possible links between the cited output and institutional affiliations of citing outputs into bins as defined by the type of citing actor, i.e., institutions, countries, subregions, and regions, and also the citing outputs by fields of research. We present various findings in terms of both means and medians, as both have their advantages and disadvantages in dealing with outliers, high number of repeat observations, etc., together along with other distributional analyses, to compare the performance of OA outputs and closed outputs in citation diversity.

Section A: Summary statistics for the overall data

The following figures present various summary statistics for our overall data. The top-left figure shows the overall number of outputs (with DOIs) that are included in our study. These are grouped into their respective publication year as per Crossref metadata records. The top-right figure shows the yearly comparison between the amount of OA versus non-OA outputs. There is a clear increase in the proportion of OA outputs over the ten-year period. The bottom two figures depict the comparisons of mean and median, respectively, number of citations received by outputs across different OA categories. There is a clear and consistent signal of OA outputs receiving more citations when looking at the whole data set overall.

Figure: Annual DOI counts

Figure: Annual OA versus non-OA DOI counts

Figure: The mean citation count per OA category

Figure: The median citation count per OA category

Section B: Number of unique citing actors - mean and median

The following figures track the mean and median numbers of unique citing actors over time and compares them across different OA categories and for closed outputs. For example, to calculate the number of unique citing countries for a particular output, we count the number of (unique) countries for which its citing outputs are affiliated to. The main finding here is that OA outputs garner more unique citing actors almost consistently over time. Furthermore, outputs that are Green OA garner the highest number of unique citing actors. We do note however that outputs published Gold OA are also likely to be published Green OA. This means these outputs potentially gets the benefits of both routes of OA. We also note that flat pattern for the median number of unique citing regions is the result of low number of possible regions, and a similar pattern is shown for the median number of unique citing fields due to most citations occurring within-field for a large portion of outputs that have low citation counts.

Figure: The mean number of unique citing Institutions

Figure: The median number of unique citing Institutions

Figure: The mean number of unique citing Countries

Figure: The median number of unique citing Countries

Figure: The mean number of unique citing Subregions

Figure: The median number of unique citing Subregions

Figure: The mean number of unique citing Fields

Figure: The median number of unique citing Fields

Figure: The mean number of unique citing Regions

Figure: The median number of unique citing Regions

Section C: Number of unique citing actors - box plots

This section extends the comparison of unique citing actors to their respective distributions, as represented by box plots. To ensure robust comparisons, we sample 10,000 outputs independently from each OA category and closed outputs, for each year of publication. The quartiles of numbers of unique citing actors are shown together with potential outliers in each category. The general pattern observed is that OA outputs attract higher numbers of unique citing actors, which is signalled both by the distributional differences and many more outliers in the upper tail. Again, it is noted that this general pattern can be diluted by the low number of regions in the regional comparisons. For the cases of institutions, the very high numbers of upper outliers skew the figures but the general pattern applies.

The first set of these is based on Institutions as citing actors:

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Institutions by OA status for 2010
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Institutions by OA status for 2011
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Institutions by OA status for 2012
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Institutions by OA status for 2013
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Institutions by OA status for 2014
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Institutions by OA status for 2015
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Institutions by OA status for 2016
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Institutions by OA status for 2017
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Institutions by OA status for 2018
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Institutions by OA status for 2019
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

The next set is based on Countries as citing actors:

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Countries by OA status for 2010
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Countries by OA status for 2011
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Countries by OA status for 2012
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Countries by OA status for 2013
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Countries by OA status for 2014
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Countries by OA status for 2015
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Countries by OA status for 2016
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Countries by OA status for 2017
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Countries by OA status for 2018
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Countries by OA status for 2019
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

The next set is based on Subregions as citing actors:

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Subregions by OA status for 2010
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Subregions by OA status for 2011
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Subregions by OA status for 2012
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Subregions by OA status for 2013
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Subregions by OA status for 2014
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Subregions by OA status for 2015
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Subregions by OA status for 2016
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Subregions by OA status for 2017
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Subregions by OA status for 2018
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Subregions by OA status for 2019
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

The next set is based on Regions as citing actors:

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Regions by OA status for 2010
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Regions by OA status for 2011
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Regions by OA status for 2012
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Regions by OA status for 2013
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Regions by OA status for 2014
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Regions by OA status for 2015
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Regions by OA status for 2016
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Regions by OA status for 2017
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Regions by OA status for 2018
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Regions by OA status for 2019
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

The next set is based on the Fields as citing actors:

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Fields by OA status for 2010
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Fields by OA status for 2011
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Fields by OA status for 2012
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Fields by OA status for 2013
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Fields by OA status for 2014
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Fields by OA status for 2015
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Fields by OA status for 2016
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Fields by OA status for 2017
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Fields by OA status for 2018
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Fields by OA status for 2019
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Section D: Citation diversity scores - mean and median

In this section, we present the summary results of the diversity scores for outputs in the various OA categories. Here, we include all outputs in our study. In the following figures, mean and median diversity scores are tracked over ten years. This is plotted for various combinations of diversity measure and citing actor types. Throughout the different measures across different citing actors, we find OA outputs to score higher in diversity. This is also consistently observed for all years included in the analysis. Green OA seems to lead in the diversity scores, which is also consistent with earlier comparisons on numbers of unique citing actors.

The first set of these is based on the Gini-Simpson index:

Figure: The mean GiniSim index of citing Institutions

Figure: The median GiniSim index of citing Institutions

Figure: The mean GiniSim index of citing Countries

Figure: The median GiniSim index of citing Countries

Figure: The mean GiniSim index of citing Subregions

Figure: The median GiniSim index of citing Subregions

Figure: The mean GiniSim index of citing Regions

Figure: The median GiniSim index of citing Regions

Figure: The mean GiniSim index of citing Fields

Figure: The median GiniSim index of citing Fields

The next set is based on the Shannon index:

Figure: The mean Shannon index of citing Institutions

Figure: The median Shannon index of citing Institutions

Figure: The mean Shannon index of citing Countries

Figure: The median Shannon index of citing Countries

Figure: The mean Shannon index of citing Subregions

Figure: The median Shannon index of citing Subregions

Figure: The mean Shannon index of citing Regions

Figure: The median Shannon index of citing Regions

Figure: The mean Shannon index of citing Fields

Figure: The median Shannon index of citing Fields

Section E: Citation diversity scores - box plots

In the following figures, the distributions of diversity scores of outputs (as per citing actor type) of different OA categories are compared. Random samples of 10,000 outputs from each OA category and 10,000 closed outputs are used in this comparison. The skewness towards the lower tails in the case of Gini-Simpson index scores is driven by the high number of outputs that receives low number of citations (hence low diversity scores). In line with earlier findings, OA outputs produce higher diversity scores. Again, it is interesting to note the raised distribution of Green OA compared to other categories. The non-OA category consistently have a longer lower tail in the Gini-Simpson scores, while Green OA outputs often have the shortest lower tail. For the Shannon index, a parallel observation can be made with non-OA outputs producing shorter upper tails. We note again the small number effect on some figures.

The first set of these is based on the Gini-Simpson index and institutions as citing actors:

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Institutions by OA status for 2016 (samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Institutions by OA status for 2017 (samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Institutions by OA status for 2018 (samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Institutions by OA status for 2019 (samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

The next set is based on the Gini-Simpson index and countries as citing actors:

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Countries by OA status for 2010 (samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Countries by OA status for 2011 (samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Countries by OA status for 2012 (samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Countries by OA status for 2013 (samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Countries by OA status for 2014 (samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Countries by OA status for 2015 (samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Subregions by OA status for 2016
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Subregions by OA status for 2017
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Subregions by OA status for 2018
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Subregions by OA status for 2019
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

The next set is based on the Gini-Simpson index and Regions as citing actors:

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Regions by OA status for 2010
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Regions by OA status for 2011
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Regions by OA status for 2012
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Regions by OA status for 2013
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Regions by OA status for 2014
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Regions by OA status for 2015
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Regions by OA status for 2016
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Regions by OA status for 2017
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Regions by OA status for 2018
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Regions by OA status for 2019
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

The next set is based on the Gini-Simpson index and Fields as citing actors:

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Fields by OA status for 2010
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Fields by OA status for 2011
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Fields by OA status for 2012
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Fields by OA status for 2013
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Fields by OA status for 2014
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Fields by OA status for 2015
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Fields by OA status for 2016 (samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Fields by OA status for 2017 (samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Fields by OA status for 2018 (samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Fields by OA status for 2019 (samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

The next set is based on the Shannon index and institutions as citing actors:

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Institutions by OA status for 2010 (samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Institutions by OA status for 2011 (samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Institutions by OA status for 2012 (samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Institutions by OA status for 2013 (samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Institutions by OA status for 2014 (samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Institutions by OA status for 2015 (samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Subregions by OA status for 2016
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Subregions by OA status for 2017
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Subregions by OA status for 2018
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Subregions by OA status for 2019
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

The next set is based on the Shannon index and Regions as citing actors:

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Regions by OA status for 2010
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Regions by OA status for 2011
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Regions by OA status for 2012
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Regions by OA status for 2013
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Regions by OA status for 2014
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Regions by OA status for 2015
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Fields by OA status for 2016
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Fields by OA status for 2017
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Fields by OA status for 2018
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Fields by OA status for 2019
(samples of 10000 non-OA, 10000 OA, 10000 gold and 10000 green papers.)

Section F: Citation diversity scores - density estimation

We apply kernel density estimation (KDE) to citation diversity scores for each year, type of citing actor, and diversity measure. These are paired with the corresponding histograms. Samples used contain 10,000 OA outputs and 10,000 non-OA outputs for each publication year. These graphs provide overviews of the distributions of citation diversity scores. The clusters around zero, and around 0.5 for Gini-Simpson index and around 0.6 for Shannon index, are results of large portions of low-citation outputs. The most important signal from these graphs is the consistently better performance of the OA outputs. This can be seen from the upward shifts of the distributions, decreases of proportions of outputs with low scores (including the cluster around zero), and the heavier upper tails, for the OA outputs.

The first set of these is based on the Gini-Simpson index and institutions as citing actors:

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Institutions for 2010

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Institutions for 2011

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Institutions for 2012

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Institutions for 2013

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Institutions for 2014

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Institutions for 2015

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Institutions for 2016

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Institutions for 2017

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Institutions for 2018

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Institutions for 2019

The first set of these is based on the Gini-Simpson index and countries as citing actors:

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Countries for 2010

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Countries for 2011

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Countries for 2012

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Countries for 2013

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Countries for 2014

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Countries for 2015

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Countries for 2016

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Countries for 2017

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Subregions for 2018

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Subregions for 2019

The first set of these is based on the Gini-Simpson index and regions as citing actors:

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Regions for 2010

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Regions for 2011

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Regions for 2012

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Regions for 2013

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Regions for 2014

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Regions for 2015

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Regions for 2016

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Regions for 2017

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Fields for 2018

Figure: KDE of GiniSim scores on citing Fields for 2019

The first set of these is based on the Shannon index and institutions as citing actors:

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Institutions for 2010

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Institutions for 2011

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Institutions for 2012

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Institutions for 2013

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Institutions for 2014

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Institutions for 2015

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Institutions for 2016

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Institutions for 2017

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Institutions for 2018

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Institutions for 2019

The first set of these is based on the Shannon index and countries as citing actors:

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Countries for 2010

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Countries for 2011

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Countries for 2012

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Countries for 2013

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Countries for 2014

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Countries for 2015

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Countries for 2016

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Countries for 2017

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Countries for 2018

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Countries for 2019

The first set of these is based on the Shannon index and subregions as citing actors:

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Subregions for 2010

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Subregions for 2011

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Subregions for 2012

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Subregions for 2013

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Subregions for 2014

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Subregions for 2015

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Subregions for 2016

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Subregions for 2017

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Regions for 2018

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Regions for 2019

The first set of these is based on the Shannon index and fields as citing actors:

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Fields for 2010

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Fields for 2011

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Fields for 2012

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Fields for 2013

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Fields for 2014

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Fields for 2015

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Fields for 2016

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Fields for 2017

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Fields for 2018

Figure: KDE of Shannon scores on citing Fields for 2019

Section G: Citation diversity scores - comparing fields of research

This section explores the OA effect on citation diversity as per field of research. For each field of research (as defined by the MAG Level 0 fields), we track the mean and median Shannon and Gini-Simpson scores for the OA categories and for closed outputs, as per type of citing actor. For most fields of research, we find Green OA as the standout performer. Performance of overall OA and Gold OA varies widely for selected fields.

For Gini-Simpson scores on citing institutions:

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Institutions for Art

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Institutions for Art

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Institutions for Biology

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Institutions for Biology

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Institutions for Business

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Institutions for Business

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Institutions for Chemistry

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Institutions for Chemistry

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Institutions for Computer science

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Institutions for Computer science

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Institutions for Economics

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Institutions for Economics

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Institutions for Engineering

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Institutions for Engineering

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Institutions for Environmental science

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Institutions for Environmental science

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Institutions for Geography

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Institutions for Geography

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Institutions for Geology

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Institutions for Geology

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Institutions for History

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Institutions for History

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Institutions for Materials science

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Institutions for Materials science

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Institutions for Mathematics

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Institutions for Mathematics

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Institutions for Medicine

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Institutions for Medicine

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Institutions for Philosophy

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Institutions for Philosophy

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Institutions for Physics

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Institutions for Physics

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Institutions for Political science

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Institutions for Political science

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Institutions for Psychology

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Institutions for Psychology

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Institutions for Sociology

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Institutions for Sociology

For Shannon scores on citing institutions:

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Institutions for Art

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Institutions for Art

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Institutions for Biology

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Institutions for Biology

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Institutions for Business

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Institutions for Business

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Institutions for Chemistry

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Institutions for Chemistry

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Institutions for Computer science

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Institutions for Computer science

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Institutions for Economics

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Institutions for Economics

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Institutions for Engineering

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Institutions for Engineering

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Institutions for Environmental science

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Institutions for Environmental science

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Institutions for Geography

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Institutions for Geography

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Institutions for Geology

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Institutions for Geology

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Institutions for History

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Institutions for History

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Institutions for Materials science

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Institutions for Materials science

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Institutions for Mathematics

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Institutions for Mathematics

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Institutions for Medicine

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Institutions for Medicine

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Institutions for Philosophy

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Institutions for Philosophy

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Institutions for Physics

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Institutions for Physics

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Institutions for Political science

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Institutions for Political science

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Institutions for Psychology

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Institutions for Psychology

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Institutions for Sociology

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Institutions for Sociology

For Gini-Simpson scores on citing countries:

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Countries for Art

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Countries for Art

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Countries for Biology

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Countries for Biology

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Countries for Business

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Countries for Business

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Countries for Chemistry

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Countries for Chemistry

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Countries for Computer science

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Countries for Computer science

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Countries for Economics

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Countries for Economics

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Countries for Engineering

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Countries for Engineering

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Countries for Environmental science

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Countries for Environmental science

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Countries for Geography

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Countries for Geography

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Countries for Geology

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Countries for Geology

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Countries for History

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Countries for History

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Countries for Materials science

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Countries for Materials science

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Countries for Mathematics

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Countries for Mathematics

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Countries for Medicine

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Countries for Medicine

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Countries for Philosophy

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Countries for Philosophy

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Countries for Physics

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Countries for Physics

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Countries for Political science

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Countries for Political science

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Countries for Psychology

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Countries for Psychology

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Countries for Sociology

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Countries for Sociology

For Shannon scores on citing countries:

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Countries for Art

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Countries for Art

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Countries for Biology

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Countries for Biology

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Countries for Business

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Countries for Business

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Countries for Chemistry

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Countries for Chemistry

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Countries for Computer science

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Countries for Computer science

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Countries for Economics

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Countries for Economics

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Countries for Engineering

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Countries for Engineering

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Countries for Environmental science

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Countries for Environmental science

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Countries for Geography

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Countries for Geography

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Countries for Geology

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Countries for Geology

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Countries for History

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Countries for History

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Countries for Materials science

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Countries for Materials science

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Countries for Mathematics

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Countries for Mathematics

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Countries for Medicine

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Countries for Medicine

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Countries for Philosophy

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Countries for Philosophy

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Countries for Physics

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Countries for Physics

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Countries for Political science

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Countries for Political science

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Countries for Psychology

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Countries for Psychology

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Countries for Sociology

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Countries for Sociology

For Gini-Simpson scores on citing subregions:

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Subregions for Art

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Subregions for Art

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Subregions for Biology

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Subregions for Biology

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Subregions for Business

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Subregions for Business

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Subregions for Chemistry

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Subregions for Chemistry

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Subregions for Computer science

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Subregions for Computer science

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Subregions for Economics

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Subregions for Economics

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Subregions for Engineering

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Subregions for Engineering

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Subregions for Environmental science

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Subregions for Environmental science

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Subregions for Geography

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Subregions for Geography

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Subregions for Geology

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Subregions for Geology

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Subregions for History

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Subregions for History

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Subregions for Materials science

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Subregions for Materials science

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Subregions for Mathematics

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Subregions for Mathematics

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Subregions for Medicine

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Subregions for Medicine

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Subregions for Philosophy

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Subregions for Philosophy

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Subregions for Physics

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Subregions for Physics

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Subregions for Political science

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Subregions for Political science

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Subregions for Psychology

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Subregions for Psychology

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Subregions for Sociology

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Subregions for Sociology

For Shannon scores on citing subregions:

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Subregions for Art

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Subregions for Art

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Subregions for Biology

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Subregions for Biology

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Subregions for Business

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Subregions for Business

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Subregions for Chemistry

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Subregions for Chemistry

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Subregions for Computer science

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Subregions for Computer science

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Subregions for Economics

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Subregions for Economics

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Subregions for Engineering

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Subregions for Engineering

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Subregions for Environmental science

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Subregions for Environmental science

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Subregions for Geography

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Subregions for Geography

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Subregions for Geology

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Subregions for Geology

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Subregions for History

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Subregions for History

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Subregions for Materials science

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Subregions for Materials science

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Subregions for Mathematics

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Subregions for Mathematics

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Subregions for Medicine

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Subregions for Medicine

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Subregions for Philosophy

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Subregions for Philosophy

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Subregions for Physics

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Subregions for Physics

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Subregions for Political science

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Subregions for Political science

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Subregions for Psychology

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Subregions for Psychology

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Subregions for Sociology

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Subregions for Sociology

For Gini-Simpson scores on citing regions:

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Regions for Art

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Regions for Art

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Regions for Biology

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Regions for Biology

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Regions for Business

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Regions for Business

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Regions for Chemistry

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Regions for Chemistry

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Regions for Computer science

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Regions for Computer science

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Regions for Economics

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Regions for Economics

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Regions for Engineering

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Regions for Engineering

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Regions for Environmental science

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Regions for Environmental science

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Regions for Geography

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Regions for Geography

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Regions for Geology

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Regions for Geology

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Regions for History

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Regions for History

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Regions for Materials science

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Regions for Materials science

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Regions for Mathematics

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Regions for Mathematics

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Regions for Medicine

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Regions for Medicine

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Regions for Philosophy

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Regions for Philosophy

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Regions for Physics

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Regions for Physics

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Regions for Political science

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Regions for Political science

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Regions for Psychology

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Regions for Psychology

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Regions for Sociology

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Regions for Sociology

For Shannon scores on citing regions:

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Regions for Art

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Regions for Art

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Regions for Biology

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Regions for Biology

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Regions for Business

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Regions for Business

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Regions for Chemistry

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Regions for Chemistry

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Regions for Computer science

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Regions for Computer science

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Regions for Economics

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Regions for Economics

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Regions for Engineering

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Regions for Engineering

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Regions for Environmental science

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Regions for Environmental science

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Regions for Geography

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Regions for Geography

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Regions for Geology

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Regions for Geology

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Regions for History

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Regions for History

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Regions for Materials science

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Regions for Materials science

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Regions for Mathematics

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Regions for Mathematics

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Regions for Medicine

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Regions for Medicine

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Regions for Philosophy

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Regions for Philosophy

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Regions for Physics

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Regions for Physics

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Regions for Political science

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Regions for Political science

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Regions for Psychology

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Regions for Psychology

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Regions for Sociology

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Regions for Sociology

For Gini-Simpson scores on citing fields:

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Fields for Art

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Fields for Art

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Fields for Biology

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Fields for Biology

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Fields for Business

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Fields for Business

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Fields for Chemistry

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Fields for Chemistry

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Fields for Computer science

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Fields for Computer science

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Fields for Economics

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Fields for Economics

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Fields for Engineering

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Fields for Engineering

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Fields for Environmental science

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Fields for Environmental science

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Fields for Geography

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Fields for Geography

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Fields for Geology

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Fields for Geology

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Fields for History

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Fields for History

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Fields for Materials science

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Fields for Materials science

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Fields for Mathematics

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Fields for Mathematics

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Fields for Medicine

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Fields for Medicine

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Fields for Philosophy

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Fields for Philosophy

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Fields for Physics

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Fields for Physics

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Fields for Political science

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Fields for Political science

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Fields for Psychology

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Fields for Psychology

Figure: Comparing mean GiniSim on citing Fields for Sociology

Figure: Comparing median GiniSim on citing Fields for Sociology

For Shannon scores on citing fields:

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Fields for Art

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Fields for Art

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Fields for Biology

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Fields for Biology

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Fields for Business

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Fields for Business

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Fields for Chemistry

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Fields for Chemistry

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Fields for Computer science

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Fields for Computer science

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Fields for Economics

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Fields for Economics

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Fields for Engineering

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Fields for Engineering

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Fields for Environmental science

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Fields for Environmental science

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Fields for Geography

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Fields for Geography

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Fields for Geology

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Fields for Geology

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Fields for History

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Fields for History

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Fields for Materials science

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Fields for Materials science

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Fields for Mathematics

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Fields for Mathematics

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Fields for Medicine

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Fields for Medicine

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Fields for Philosophy

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Fields for Philosophy

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Fields for Physics

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Fields for Physics

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Fields for Political science

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Fields for Political science

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Fields for Psychology

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Fields for Psychology

Figure: Comparing mean Shannon on citing Fields for Sociology

Figure: Comparing median Shannon on citing Fields for Sociology

Section H: Citation groups vs number of unique citing actors

In this section, we split the outputs into groups depending on citation numbers and by OA/non-OA status. The sample of outputs includes 2,000 OA outputs and 2,000 non-OA outputs from each citation group (i.e., 56,000 outputs in total), as per publication year. The number of unique citing actors is counted for each output and compared across citation groups. This is to check whether the OA advantage observed in the previous sections remain consistent across the levels of citation. As expected, the number of unique citing actors may increase with the number of citations. However, the OA advantage also seems to remain in place irrespective of the level of citation. Again, we note that the level of effect of the OA advantage can be less obvious when the total numbers of potential counts are low. The performance of OA outputs appears to be at least as good, or better, than the non-OA outputs.

The first set of these is based on Institutions as citing actors:

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Institutions by citation groups for 2010
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Institutions by citation groups for 2011
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Institutions by citation groups for 2012
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Institutions by citation groups for 2013
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Institutions by citation groups for 2014
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Institutions by citation groups for 2015
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Institutions by citation groups for 2016
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Institutions by citation groups for 2017
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Institutions by citation groups for 2018
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Institutions by citation groups for 2019
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

The next set is based on Countries as citing actors:

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Countries by citation groups for 2010
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Countries by citation groups for 2011
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Countries by citation groups for 2012
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Countries by citation groups for 2013
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Countries by citation groups for 2014
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Countries by citation groups for 2015
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Countries by citation groups for 2016
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Countries by citation groups for 2017
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Countries by citation groups for 2018
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Countries by citation groups for 2019
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

The next set is based on Subregions as citing actors:

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Subregions by citation groups for 2010
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Subregions by citation groups for 2011
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Subregions by citation groups for 2012
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Subregions by citation groups for 2013
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Subregions by citation groups for 2014
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Subregions by citation groups for 2015
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Subregions by citation groups for 2016
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Subregions by citation groups for 2017
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Subregions by citation groups for 2018
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Subregions by citation groups for 2019
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

The next set is based on Regions as citing actors:

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Regions by citation groups for 2010
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Regions by citation groups for 2011
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Regions by citation groups for 2012
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Regions by citation groups for 2013
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Regions by citation groups for 2014
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Regions by citation groups for 2015
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Regions by citation groups for 2016
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Regions by citation groups for 2017
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Regions by citation groups for 2018
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Regions by citation groups for 2019
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

The next set is based on the Fields as citing actors:

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Fields by citation groups for 2010
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Fields by citation groups for 2011
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Fields by citation groups for 2012
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Fields by citation groups for 2013
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Fields by citation groups for 2014
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Fields by citation groups for 2015
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Fields by citation groups for 2016
 (A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Fields by citation groups for 2017
 (A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Fields by citation groups for 2018
 (A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of number of unique citing Fields by citation groups for 2019
 (A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Section I: Citation groups vs citation diversity scores

Similar to the previous section, outputs are split into groups by citation counts - 2,000 OA outputs and 2,000 non-OA outputs are sampled from each citation group. A diversity score is calculated based on citing actors for each output and boxplot constructed for OA and non-OA outputs. Each figure below represent the findings for each type of citing actor and each publication year. Not unexpectedly the increase in citation count may correlate with slightly higher diversity scores for both diversity measures (i.e., higher likelihood of different citing actors). The general pattern that OA outputs scoring higher in diversity remains consistent through citation groups, types of citing actors, publication years, and across diversity measures.

The first set of these is based on the Gini-Simpson index and institutions as citing actors:

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Institutions by citation groups for 2010 (A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Institutions by citation groups for 2011 (A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Institutions by citation groups for 2012 (A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Institutions by citation groups for 2013 (A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Institutions by citation groups for 2014 (A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Institutions by citation groups for 2015 (A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Institutions by citation groups for 2016 (A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Institutions by citation groups for 2017 (A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Institutions by citation groups for 2018
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Institutions by citation groups for 2019
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

The next set is based on the Gini-Simpson index and countries as citing actors:

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Countries by citation groups for 2010
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Countries by citation groups for 2011
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Countries by citation groups for 2012
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Countries by citation groups for 2013
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Countries by citation groups for 2014
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Countries by citation groups for 2015
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Countries by citation groups for 2016
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Countries by citation groups for 2017
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Subregions by citation groups for 2018
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Subregions by citation groups for 2019
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

The next set is based on the Gini-Simpson index and Regions as citing actors:

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Regions by citation groups for 2010
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Regions by citation groups for 2011
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Regions by citation groups for 2012
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Regions by citation groups for 2013
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Regions by citation groups for 2014
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Regions by citation groups for 2015
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Regions by citation groups for 2016
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Regions by citation groups for 2017
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Regions by citation groups for 2018
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Regions by citation groups for 2019
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

The next set is based on the Gini-Simpson index and Fields as citing actors:

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Fields by citation groups for 2010
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Fields by citation groups for 2011
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Fields by citation groups for 2012
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Fields by citation groups for 2013
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Fields by citation groups for 2014
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Fields by citation groups for 2015
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Fields by citation groups for 2016
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of GiniSim index on citing Fields by citation groups for 2017
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Institutions by citation groups for 2018
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Institutions by citation groups for 2019
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

The next set is based on the Shannon index and countries as citing actors:

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Countries by citation groups for 2010
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Countries by citation groups for 2011
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Countries by citation groups for 2012
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Countries by citation groups for 2013
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Countries by citation groups for 2014
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Countries by citation groups for 2015
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Countries by citation groups for 2016
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Countries by citation groups for 2017
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Countries by citation groups for 2018
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Countries by citation groups for 2019
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

The next set is based on the Shannon index and Subregions as citing actors:

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Subregions by citation groups for 2010
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Subregions by citation groups for 2011
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Subregions by citation groups for 2012
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Subregions by citation groups for 2013
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Subregions by citation groups for 2014
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Subregions by citation groups for 2015
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Subregions by citation groups for 2016
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Subregions by citation groups for 2017
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Fields by citation groups for 2018
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Figure: Box plots of Shannon index on citing Fields by citation groups for 2019
(A total of 56000 papers. Each group consists of a sample 2000 OA papers and 2000 non-OA papers)

Section J: Citation counts vs citation diversity scores

In the following figures, quartiles of diversity scores are tracked against citation counts for the complete data set. Instead of sampling outputs by citation groups in the previous section, we include all outputs in the study in the following analysis and all citation counts (not groups). This is plotted for various combinations of diversity measure, type of citing actors and publication year. Results with fields of research as citing actors are excluded, as no meaningful results are produced due to very small numbers (i.e., most outputs are cited within very few fields). The aim is to further explore potential relationships between diversity scores and citation counts. Interestingly, the mild positive relationship between diversity scores and citation counts observed in the lower end of the spectrum (which is consistent with the previous section) seems to fade away as we move towards outputs with very high citations. Hence, in most cases, diversity scores are not completely driven by citation counts.

The first set of these is based on the Gini-Simpson index and institutions as citing actors:

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Institutions for 2010

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Institutions for 2011

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Institutions for 2012

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Institutions for 2013

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Institutions for 2014

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Institutions for 2015

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Institutions for 2016

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Institutions for 2017

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Institutions for 2018

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Institutions for 2019

The next set is based on the Gini-Simpson index and countries as citing actors:

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Countries for 2010

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Countries for 2011

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Countries for 2012

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Countries for 2013

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Countries for 2014

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Countries for 2015

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Countries for 2016

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Countries for 2017

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Countries for 2018

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Countries for 2019

The next set is based on the Gini-Simpson index and Subregions as citing actors:

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Subregions for 2010

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Subregions for 2011

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Subregions for 2012

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Subregions for 2013

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Subregions for 2014

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Subregions for 2015

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Subregions for 2016

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Subregions for 2017

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Subregions for 2018

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Subregions for 2019

The next set is based on the Gini-Simpson index and Regions as citing actors:

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Regions for 2010

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Regions for 2011

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Regions for 2012

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Regions for 2013

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Regions for 2014

Figure: Citation count versus GiniSim index of citing Regions for 2015

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Institutions for 2016

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Institutions for 2017

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Institutions for 2018

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Institutions for 2019

The next set is based on the Shannon index and countries as citing actors:

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Countries for 2010

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Countries for 2011

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Countries for 2012

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Countries for 2013

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Countries for 2014

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Countries for 2015

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Countries for 2016

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Countries for 2017

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Countries for 2018

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Countries for 2019

The next set is based on the Shannon index and Subregions as citing actors:

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Subregions for 2010

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Subregions for 2011

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Subregions for 2012

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Subregions for 2013

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Subregions for 2014

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Subregions for 2015

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Subregions for 2016

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Subregions for 2017

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Subregions for 2018

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Subregions for 2019

The next set is based on the Shannon index and Regions as citing actors:

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Regions for 2010

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Regions for 2011

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Regions for 2012

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Regions for 2013

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Regions for 2014

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Regions for 2015

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Regions for 2016

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Regions for 2017

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Regions for 2018

Figure: Citation count versus Shannon index of citing Regions for 2019

Section K: OA citation advantage for subregions using average citation ratios

This section explores the OA citation advantage in terms of how much more citations OA outputs garner, on average, over time. The average citation ratio (i.e., percentage ratio in average citation) is calculated as the average number of citations to OA outputs, divided by the average number of citations to non-OA outputs, and times by one hundred. For outputs affiliated to a given subregion, this percentage is calculated for all inward citations from each subregion, for each of the ten-year period. A value above 100% indicates the set of OA outputs attracts more citations than the corresponding set of non-OA outputs, from a specific subregion in that year.

Figure: % ratios in average citations to papers affiliated to Eastern Asia
(% ratios are calculated based on citations to OA over non-OA papers)

Figure: % ratios in average citations to papers affiliated to Southern Asia
(% ratios are calculated based on citations to OA over non-OA papers)

Figure: % ratios in average citations to papers affiliated to Western Asia
(% ratios are calculated based on citations to OA over non-OA papers)

Figure: % ratios in average citations to papers affiliated to South-eastern Asia
(% ratios are calculated based on citations to OA over non-OA papers)

Figure: % ratios in average citations to papers affiliated to Central Asia
(% ratios are calculated based on citations to OA over non-OA papers)

Figure: % ratios in average citations to papers affiliated to Southern Europe
(% ratios are calculated based on citations to OA over non-OA papers)

Figure: % ratios in average citations to papers affiliated to Eastern Europe
(% ratios are calculated based on citations to OA over non-OA papers)

Figure: % ratios in average citations to papers affiliated to Western Europe
(% ratios are calculated based on citations to OA over non-OA papers)

Section L: OA citation advantage for regions using average citation ratios

Continuing from the previous section, the corresponding results for regions are presented here. Similar to the previous section, there appears to be something peculiar with outputs affiliated to Asia and Asian subregions. This is potentially the result of several factors. First, our data's coverage of the Chinese language publications are relatively low as a result of using only Crossref DOIs. Secondly, Asia-affiliated outputs in our data show a lower level of OA as compared to other regions.

Section M: OA citation advantage for subregions using percentage change in total citations

In this section we take an alternative look at where citations are coming from. Total citation numbers are used to calculate the percentage changes, i.e., total citations to OA outputs minus total citations to non-OA outputs, then divided by total citations to non-OA outputs, and multiplied by one hundred. We note that the levels of OA are lower in earlier years as compared to more recent years and this has an effect on the total citation counts. As the level of OA becomes more comparable with the proportion of non-OA outputs (more recent years), the effect of OA becomes far more clear. While the general trend is that most subregions benefits from received increased citations, there are subregions that benefits more than others, i.e., Northern America and Western Europe. However, there are also signals that some traditionally disadvantaged subregions benefiting greatly from OA, such as Sub-Saharan Africa.

For outputs affiliated to Eastern Asia:

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Eastern Asia for 2010

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Eastern Asia for 2011

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Eastern Asia for 2012

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Eastern Asia for 2013

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Eastern Asia for 2014

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Eastern Asia for 2015

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Eastern Asia for 2016

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Eastern Asia for 2017

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Eastern Asia for 2018

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Eastern Asia for 2019

For outputs affiliated to Southern Asia:

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Southern Asia for 2010

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Southern Asia for 2011

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Southern Asia for 2012

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Southern Asia for 2013

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Southern Asia for 2014

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Southern Asia for 2015

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Southern Asia for 2016

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Southern Asia for 2017

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Southern Asia for 2018

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Southern Asia for 2019

For outputs affiliated to Western Asia:

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Western Asia for 2010

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Western Asia for 2011

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Western Asia for 2012

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Western Asia for 2013

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Western Asia for 2014

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Western Asia for 2015

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Western Asia for 2016

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Western Asia for 2017

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Western Asia for 2018

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Western Asia for 2019

For outputs affiliated to South-eastern Asia:

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to South-eastern Asia for 2010

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to South-eastern Asia for 2011

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to South-eastern Asia for 2012

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to South-eastern Asia for 2013

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to South-eastern Asia for 2014

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to South-eastern Asia for 2015

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to South-eastern Asia for 2016

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to South-eastern Asia for 2017

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to South-eastern Asia for 2018

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to South-eastern Asia for 2019

For outputs affiliated to Central Asia:

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Central Asia for 2010

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Central Asia for 2011

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Central Asia for 2012

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Central Asia for 2013

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Central Asia for 2014

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Central Asia for 2015

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Central Asia for 2016

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Central Asia for 2017

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Central Asia for 2018

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Central Asia for 2019

For outputs affiliated to Southern Europe:

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Southern Europe for 2010

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Southern Europe for 2011

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Southern Europe for 2012

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Southern Europe for 2013

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Southern Europe for 2014

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Southern Europe for 2015

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Southern Europe for 2016

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Southern Europe for 2017

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Southern Europe for 2018

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Southern Europe for 2019

For outputs affiliated to Eastern Europe:

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Eastern Europe for 2010

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Eastern Europe for 2011

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Eastern Europe for 2012

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Eastern Europe for 2013

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Eastern Europe for 2014

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Eastern Europe for 2015

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Eastern Europe for 2016

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Eastern Europe for 2017

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Eastern Europe for 2018

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Eastern Europe for 2019

For outputs affiliated to Western Europe:

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Western Europe for 2010

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Western Europe for 2011

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Western Europe for 2012

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Western Europe for 2013

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Western Europe for 2014

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Western Europe for 2015

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Western Europe for 2016

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Western Europe for 2017

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Western Europe for 2018

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Western Europe for 2019

For outputs affiliated to Northern Europe:

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern Europe for 2010

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern Europe for 2011

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern Europe for 2012

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern Europe for 2013

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern Europe for 2014

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern Europe for 2015

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern Europe for 2016

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern Europe for 2017

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern Europe for 2018

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern Europe for 2019

For outputs affiliated to Latin America and the Caribbean:

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Latin America and the Caribbean for 2010

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Latin America and the Caribbean for 2011

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Latin America and the Caribbean for 2012

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Latin America and the Caribbean for 2013

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Latin America and the Caribbean for 2014

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Latin America and the Caribbean for 2015

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Latin America and the Caribbean for 2016

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Latin America and the Caribbean for 2017

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Latin America and the Caribbean for 2018

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Latin America and the Caribbean for 2019

For outputs affiliated to Northern America:

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern America for 2010

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern America for 2011

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern America for 2012

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern America for 2013

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern America for 2014

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern America for 2015

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern America for 2016

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern America for 2017

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern America for 2018

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern America for 2019

For outputs affiliated to Australia and New Zealand:

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Australia and New Zealand for 2010

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Australia and New Zealand for 2011

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Australia and New Zealand for 2012

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Australia and New Zealand for 2013

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Australia and New Zealand for 2014

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Australia and New Zealand for 2015

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Australia and New Zealand for 2016

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Australia and New Zealand for 2017

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Australia and New Zealand for 2018

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Australia and New Zealand for 2019

For outputs affiliated to Melania:

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Melania for 2010

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Melania for 2011

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Melania for 2012

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Melania for 2013

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Melania for 2014

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Melania for 2015

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Melanesia for 2016

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Melanesia for 2017

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Melanesia for 2018

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Melanesia for 2019

For outputs affiliated to Polynesia:

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Polynesia for 2010

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Polynesia for 2011

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Polynesia for 2012

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Polynesia for 2013

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Polynesia for 2014

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Polynesia for 2015

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Polynesia for 2016

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Polynesia for 2017

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Polynesia for 2018

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Polynesia for 2019

For outputs affiliated to Micronesia:

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Micronesia for 2010

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Micronesia for 2013

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Micronesia for 2017

For outputs affiliated to Northern Africa:

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern Africa for 2010

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern Africa for 2011

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern Africa for 2012

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern Africa for 2013

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern Africa for 2014

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern Africa for 2015

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern Africa for 2016

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern Africa for 2017

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern Africa for 2018

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Northern Africa for 2019

For outputs affiliated to Sub-Saharan Africa:

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Sub-Saharan Africa for 2010

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Sub-Saharan Africa for 2011

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Sub-Saharan Africa for 2012

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Sub-Saharan Africa for 2013

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Sub-Saharan Africa for 2014

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Sub-Saharan Africa for 2015

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Sub-Saharan Africa for 2016

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Sub-Saharan Africa for 2017

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Sub-Saharan Africa for 2018

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Sub-Saharan Africa for 2019

Section N: OA citation advantage for regions using percentage change in total citations

Continuing from the previous section, we present parallel results for regions below.

For outputs affiliated to Asia:

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Asia for 2010

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Asia for 2011

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Asia for 2012

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Asia for 2013

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Asia for 2014

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Asia for 2015

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Asia for 2016

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Asia for 2017

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Asia for 2018

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Asia for 2019

For outputs affiliated to Europe:

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Europe for 2010

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Europe for 2011

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Europe for 2012

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Europe for 2013

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Europe for 2014

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Europe for 2015

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Europe for 2016

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Europe for 2017

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Europe for 2018

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Europe for 2019

For outputs affiliated to Americas:

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Americas for 2010

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Americas for 2011

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Americas for 2012

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Americas for 2013

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Americas for 2014

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Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Americas for 2016

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Americas for 2017

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Americas for 2018

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Americas for 2019

For outputs affiliated to Oceania:

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Oceania for 2010

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Oceania for 2011

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Oceania for 2012

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Oceania for 2013

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Oceania for 2014

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Oceania for 2015

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Oceania for 2016

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Oceania for 2017

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Oceania for 2018

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Oceania for 2019

For outputs affiliated to Africa:

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Africa for 2010

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Africa for 2011

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Africa for 2012

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Africa for 2013

Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Africa for 2014

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Figure: % change in total citations to OA/non-OA paper affiliated to Africa for 2016

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